

LOVE IS THE KARAGA OF MERCURY

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Cite This Article: R. Panneerselvam & Dr. K. A. Velu, "Love is the Karaga of Mercury", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 7, Issue 2, Page Number 47-48, 2022.

Abstract:

Love is blind. Mercury is the dual planet. Fifth the bhava and Seventh bhava indicates love. Mercury also indicates love. There are two types of love. One is divine (true love). Other is bad (illegal sex) the conjunction of Mercury with other planets decides the nature of the love.

Key Words: Love, Saturn in Fifth Bhava, Sun with Mercury , Moon with Mercury, Moon and Mars with Mercury, Moon and Jupiter with Mercury, Moon and Venus with Mercury, Moon and Saturn with Mercury, Mars with Mercury, Jupiter with Mercury, Venus with Mercury, Saturn with Mercury, Rahu with Mercury, Kethu with Mercury, Manthi with Mercury, Jupiter and Venus with Mercury.

Introduction:

Mercury is the youthful planet. It always travels near the Sun. Venus is the planet for sex. But Mercury is the planet for love. Due to join with other planets it arranges different types of loves in our life.

Saturn in Fifth Bhava:

Any lagna Saturn stands in fifth bhava gives shame due to love affair when transit Saturn meets birth chart Saturn through conjunction / aspect one could not control his / her love affairs.

Planet conjunction with Mercury and love

Mercury with Sun:

This conjunction in first bhava / third bhava / fifth bhava / seventh bhava / ninth bhava / eleventh bhava gives love. They should love politicians or government people. They have more imaginations. They, are always attracted by flattering words.

Mercury with Moon:

This conjunction gives love without age difference. Old people should love the youngest one. This conjunction also gives more than one love. During travelling they meet the lover.

Mercury with Mars:

This conjunction gives love during their school study period or college study period. Who studies Mercury oriented education like accountancy, auditing, lawyer should afraid about parents and give up their love. But who studies Mars oriented education like engineering never afraid about parents and doing register marriage. They love the people who drives the vehicle very fast. If their parents have this same conjunction, they accept their love. If their parents haven't this same conjunction, they never accept their love.

MARS			
MERCURY			
	SON'S		
	RASI		

	MARS		
	FATHER'S	MERCURY	
	RASI		

MARS	MOTHER'S	MERCURY	
	RASI		

In above horoscope of the son: Mars and Mercury conjunction in the same house pisces.

In father's horoscope: Mars in Aries aspects Mercury in cancer as fourth aspect. So, he supports his son's love.

In mother's horoscope: Mars in Aquaris and Mercury in cancer are as 6/8 position. So, she refused his son's love.

Mercury with Jupiter:

This conjunction gives love with knowledgeable persons. They select the wise persons like teachers, professors, mentors and tutors. They will also break their love due to prestige issue.

Mercury with Venus:

This conjunction is called Mathana gopala yogam. They should love more than one person and also they should marry more than one person. Beauty is the most important factor for love. They want to marry both the elder sister and the younger sister. If the Mercury or Venus conjunction with Rahu or Kethu it gives more problems. If the Mercury or Venus conjunction with Moon, the native should be a mentally disordered one.

Mercury with Saturn:

This is the love failure conjunction. This conjunction gives bitter experience in love. Maximum one sided love comes. Their love comes at the work place or with co worker. If their love should failure, they never forget their memories of love. In future if the lovers meet again they will speak each other normally

Mercury with Rahu:

This conjunction is called as psycho love. This type native doing love after marriage. They love other's spouse illegally. Their younger sister's life is a question mark. Their married life is a painful one. After the

disappointment of the family life, they want illegal contact to fulfill their desire. They never afraid about shame and bad name.

Mercury with Kethu:

This conjunction in fifth bhava of the horoscope gives spiritual love. They love a divine person. They see their lover at temple or mutt. They never understand the difference between love and friendship. This conjunction makes love in later stage of life. Some people love their lover not really but the imaginary world.

Mercury with Mandi:

This conjunction is the most dangerous one. One should try suicide attempt. Mercury with Mandi stays in water signs is also (Cancer / Scorpio / Pisces) very very dangerous. They will die by drinking poison.

Mercury with Moon and Mars:

This conjunction natives are always straight forward. They lose their properties for love. Their love never long-lasting. They always eager to make useless travels. In female's horoscope, the native's parents oppose their love, then accept.

Mercury with Moon and Jupiter:

This conjunction is called childish love. They love the prestigious people. The native's mother supports their love and accept the love.

Mercury with Moon and Venus:

This conjunction gives a luxurious love. They listen love songs. No money, no love. They spend money wastely. They always have illegal touch.

Mercury with Moon and Saturn:

This conjunction gives love with laborious people "They want to love differently abled persons. They are cheated by their lovers later.

Mercury with Jupiter and Venus:

This conjunction gives prestigious love. They start love and quit love for prestige problem. Prestige is more than love.

Conclusion:

From this article we know the importance of Mercury in love. During the time of marriage matching we should consider the above conjunctions very well.

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